

Bridging the Gap between Accessibility and Protection

A Data Hub to host multimedia ethnographic research data on vernacular Mantra practices in Global Southern Asia adhering to the CARE-Principles

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Zusammenfassung. The transdisciplinary MANTRAMS project aims at gathering and producing large amounts of highly sensitive ethnographic audiovisual research data on religious practices and life in politically charged and socially contested spaces. Despite different publications and discipline-specific standards outlining guidelines when dealing with different aspects of such data, gaps and blindspots between them become overly apparent when adapting these expectations into transnational yet locally situated academic practice. Guided by a strong ethical commitment to transparency, data protection and sustainability, our RDM stack needs to comply with local expectations as well as the GDPR and the FAIR and CARE principles. Our efforts to build infrastructure capable of hosting vulnerable and valuable data throughout the upcoming years illustrate the depth of customisation necessary to create a safe and practical Data Hub, even when utilising as much existing data infrastructure as possible. It serves as a case study of decisionmaking in implementation and highlights the complexities and ineptitudes of RDM guidelines when stepping outside of traditional Humanities domains.

.1 MANTRAMS – Mantras in Media, Religion, and Society in Global Southern Asia

For over 3,000 years, mantras have been transmitted through spaces, media, and religious communities (Alper 2008; Rao 2019). Since September 2024, the MANTRAMS project has launched the first largescale study of this extraordinary cultural and religious body of work (ERC Synergy Grant ID 101118934, 2024-2030). Radically interdisciplinary and comparative, the project will produce a history and anthropology of mantras past and present, including extensive sonic, textual, and visual archives. MANTRAMS will reshape the field of Mantra Studies by expanding on the dominant linguistic approach to mantras as texts and focusing on *mantras as media*, as *synaesthetic* and *multisensory* as well as their *relationalities* and *power dynamics* (van Ede 2009; Ferrarini and Scaldaferrri 2020; Lee 2021; Steingo and Sykes 2019).

MANTRAMS commits to involving community members and research participants in decision-making regarding data storage, access, and sharing by applying the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance to account for the right to data sovereignty of often

marginalised communities of practitioners (Carroll et al. 2020; Rizzolli and Imeri 2022).

.2 More than data: Navigating Secrecy, Visibility, Legalities and Practicability in designing the RDM Infrastructure

Methodologically located in the fringes and intersections between the Humanities and the Social Sciences, MANTRAMS faces a unique culmination of practical, ethical and legal challenges while preparing the RDM infrastructure for data onboarding (Berry and Fagerjord 2017; Cantwell and Petersen 2021; Christen 2009; German Anthropological Association 2019; Hawkins 2021; Helling 2025; Hsu 2017; McGrail, Nieves, and Senier 2021).

Mantras are guarded by complex *local protocols of access* that need to be reflected through implementing Traditional Knowledge labels even among project members. Simultaneously, *visibility* of data co-producers is paramount: to design an infrastructure and data workflow that does not lose, and thus silence, the voices of mantra practitioners. The research data corpus will contain personal and sensitive data that are regulated heavily by the GDPR. Data will need to cross EU borders, without *EU regulations overbearing local ethics and legalities*. Lastly, the research data infrastructure needs to function in a complex academic *quotidienne*, with researchers and external collaborators moving in and out of the field with diverse expectations, analytical interests and levels of digital aptitude.

.3 Building on what is already there: A holistic approach to Infrastructure Development

We have designed a robust yet locally hosted infrastructure (re)using Open Source and *scholar-led* data infrastructure from the network of expertise at the Digital Humanities Center at the University of Tübingen. We have encountered and overcome blindspots between different dimensions of such an implementation and have funnelled these experiences into a network of trainings, guidelines and ombudspersons. At the heart of the MANTRAMS Data Hub (data.mantrams.eu) is a Nextcloud instance managed by the DHC and the project's Digital Humanities and Data Management Officer (DHDMO). Storage is provided by the DFG-funded bwSFS (Storage for Science), with identity management through bwIDM of the state of Baden-Württemberg which supports HelmholtzID and ORCID for non-German project members.

By presenting our Data Hub as a poster, we would like to invite conference participants to exchange know-how, problem stories and ideas on the issues presented above. As the (Digital) Humanities communities try to include larger cultural and historical representation, many other projects will face similar challenges and can hopefully benefit from such a use-case.

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